

Homesickness: It's Essence and Ramifications ¹

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Abstract

When a person finds themselves in a solitary state within an unfamiliar setting, there is an increased probability of them encountering the emotional state known as “Homesickness”. When an immigrant or an employee from a different country goes through the process of adapting to a new job or location, they will face various distinctive challenges. This article aims to scrutinize and assess the most significant written works on the subject of homesickness, using a systematic and critical approach. The results show that homesickness is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that affects different groups of people in different ways, and that it has significant implications for their well-being, performance, and integration. The article also discusses some of the limitations and gaps in the existing literature, and suggests some directions for future research and practice.

Keywords Individual, Alone, New environment, Psychological sensation, Homesickness, Immigrant, Employee, Nation, Unique problems.

1. Introduction

Homesickness is a psychological response that occurs when a person is confronted with a new situation and is alone (Basuki & Riani, 2018). It can be triggered by moving away from home or by experiencing social alienation in a new environment. Homesickness has been linked to various adjustment problems, health issues, and clinical disorders (Stroebe et al., 2015). The concept of homesickness has evolved over time, and it has been related to other phenomena such as culture shock, which refers to the anxiety and stress caused by coming into contact with a new culture (Lei et al., 2004). Many studies have explored the factors that contribute to homesickness and the strategies that help to cope with its negative consequences (Hack-Polay, 2012). Some scholars have come to create the phrase culture shock to describe the worry and tension caused by coming into touch with a new culture, as well as the following emotions of loss and confusion. Since Oberg's first finding, a whole area of study has sprung up around cross-cultural encounters (Lei et al., 2004). In some other literatures, homesickness was defined as “a negative emotional condition marked by craving for and concern with home, and frequently with problems adapting to a new location, mainly owing to separation from home and attachment persons.” (Nauta et al., 2020).

In today's culture, large-scale migration emphasizes the need of understanding the complicated experience of leaving home and moving inside or beyond one's own nation. Discrete kinds of stresses linked with geographic changes need distinct consideration since they are likely to be associated with different (but mutually aggravating) correlates and effects, perhaps leading to diagnosis. Homesickness (HS) is a common symptom of relocation, and it's been linked to a variety of adjustment issues, health issues, and clinical illnesses (Stroebe et al., 2015).

The goal of this study is to have a better theoretical understanding of homesickness, how the concept has born throughout time, reasons behind it and the strategies that help to cope with its consequences and negative feelings.

The process of conducting this existing research may offer some guidance and help with addressing the aforementioned problems from a theoretical perspective. The most significant literature on the subject of homesickness will be examined and discussed in this study. We shall research the effects of home sickness. This essay doesn't have a specific group in mind since it seeks to evaluate homesickness in the context of the aforementioned perspectives..

2. The origins of the concept and its evolution process

Homesickness is an illness that affects young people and old people alike who are socially isolated in other lands and can be debilitating or even lead to death. A dissertation on the subject, published in Basel in 1678 and written by physician

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Johannes Hofer was the first time that the word "nostalgia" appeared in the medical literature. The absence of refined Swiss air among Swiss soldiers stationed in France was thought to be the cause of nostalgic feelings (Rosen, 1975).

In a study performed by Baier & Welch, 1992, the concept of homesickness is examined, which follows the paradigm for concept analysis given by Chinn and Jacobs. Concept analysis is a procedure that is used to get a deeper understanding of a concept that has been discovered first via clinical practice. It is the purpose of this concept analysis to clarify and explain the idea of homesickness, and to differentiate it from other concepts such as separation anxiety, school phobia, translocation syndrome, and the consequences of relocation. The thorough definition of homesickness and the absence of homesickness has resulted in the development of criteria that may be used to other cases with comparable features to ensure that they are properly classified. In addition, research questions and nursing interventions are generated as a result of the literature evaluation and selection criteria. As a result, a study of the literature on home sickness and associated topics such as separation anxiety, school phobia, relocation consequences, and translocation syndrome has led to a thorough definition of home sickness and a concept was born

(Baier & Welch, 1992).

Furthermore, van Tilburg et al., 1999, concluded in their research that homesickness is a longing for the mentality and atmosphere of one's home environment. A distinction can be drawn between homesick subjects who exhibit signs of psychopathology, such as compulsive checking of the house, agoraphobia, adverse attachment experiences, separation anxiety, and homesickness experiences as a child, and those who do not exhibit such signs. There seems to be a more pathological type of homesickness, which appears to be linked to anxiety disorders such as agoraphobia and obsessive checking as well as poor attachment experiences and separation anxiety in childhood. This may be a form of separation anxiety characterized by an insecure or anxious attachment style. (M. A. L. van Tilburg et al., 1999).

Moreover, Stockdale's research, 2004, examines the community impacts and migrant experiences associated with present rural out-migration processes in order to link them to the future well-being of rural communities. The recent Countryside March 1 demonstrated the level of dissatisfaction and fury associated with the future of rural areas. An "endogenous or bottom-up" approach to rural development has existed for some time. Out-migration has been hidden as a research topic due to the counter-urbanization trend, which has been virtually prominent in the literature as an explanation for rural development. The purpose of this essay is to rectify this imbalance by explaining current out-migrations patterns and their consequences for current rural development initiatives (Stockdale, 2004).

According to Ferrara, 2020, homesickness is a term that encompasses an extensive range of individual thoughts, feelings, and attitudes, with a primary focus on the former home and family. Ferrara, (2020), states that Fisher and colleagues (1985) concluded after conducting a study that homesickness was a phenomenon. This research led to the discovery that some of the literature review had contradictory results (Fisher et al., 1985; Fisher & Hood 1987).

Morse & Mudgett, 2017, have carried out a study of migration, and concluded that historical investigations of homesickness tend to be centered on the longing for family and familiar constructed settings. This mixed-methods study examines the environmental nostalgia experienced by rural out-migrants in their new surroundings. From the eighteenth century to the present, Vermonters who have left the state have repeatedly voiced a desire for the natural environment. The study proposes that we broaden our conceptions of home to encompass the natural world as well. This mixed-methods study, performed by a geographer and a historian, examines the environmental nostalgia experienced by rural out-migrants in their new surroundings (Morse & Mudgett, 2017).

The study is indicating that out-migrants are the exact elements needed for rural communities to engage in rural development. In Scotland, a strategy to keep young people in rural areas is being implemented in an effort to maintain human resources. Out-migration enables a person to gain the information, skills, independence and drive to achieve that are essential for success. Exogenous or "top down" methods are required to attract the necessary human resources to depopulating regions. For rational expectations, migratory workers must return home (Morse & Mudgett, 2017).

According to the results of the survey, immigrants have a strong desire to go back to their countries of origin. Nearly everyone, at some time in their life, may experience feelings of homesickness and longing for the company of family and friends as it is simply our human nature..

3. Understanding homesickness

Understanding the meaning of homesickness is extremely important because of the vast range of negative effects it has on people's lives. The idea of homesickness is not new, and numerous research have been prepared to determine how it really affects people's social and psychological well-being.

Thurber & Walton, 2007, have indicated that homesickness has been mentioned in the Old Testament as far back as the book of Exodus and Homer's Odyssey. Hippocrates (460–377 BC) was a Greek physician who believed that homesickness was caused by an excess of black bile in the blood. The Swiss physician Johannes Hofer (1688) argued that

leaving home is a developmental milestone that everyone goes through at some point in their lives.(Thurber & Walton, 2007).

The researchers who carried out this study assert clearly that the causes for homesickness have been uncovered and are prepared to share their results with the general public. Not only so, but in addition to that, they argue that the repercussions of this occurrence may be prevented and dealt with in the event that they do occur in the future.

Scharp et al.,2016, stated in their study that even if it's in the distant past, most people feel homesick at some point in their lives. People who are feeling homesick remember events (100%), relatives (97%) emotions (100%) and locations (97%). While the majority of participants said that they did not reach out to their family and friends while they were homesick, it was found that they sought assistance both via personal means and through others. Directions for future research and practical applications are covered (Scharp et al., 2016). For many Americans, home is a source of comfort and serenity. No one knows what homesick people truly miss. Some U.S. research offers insight into the phenomena of home sickness in the United States. Findings show that daily dialogue creates home and gives it significance

4. Theories to explain homesickness

Watt & Badger,2009, indicated that according to belongingness theory, individuals have an innate need for a limited number of long-term interpersonal relationships. When people move, they leave their existing social networks and the authors propose that this may be a cause of homesickness. A further finding is that Individuals who felt accepted in their community had a decreased sense of homeliness. This has nothing to do with a significant number of friends, but shows a vital link between societal views and adaptability. Study: Homesickness is linked to the need to belong and acceptability in a new place.

Findings did not support the notion of substitution. Future study should examine the role of social ties in homesickness. This research emphasizes the value of belongingness. It also offers information relevant to belongingness theory..

5. Reasons for traveling abroad and why people leave home

According to Celik,2017, teaching in a foreign country has always provided an excellent chance for academic and social growth. Working abroad provides instructors with the opportunity to see how teachers in different nations conduct themselves in the classroom. Teachers can gain knowledge of classroom management techniques, developing lesson materials and incorporating technology into lessons. At the same time, students will broaden their understanding of the subject topic(Celik, 2017).

While working overseas, it is feasible to observe teachers. The benefits of teaching abroad are the primary emphasis of this study. As a result of the subject matter's high level of specialized nature, a customized search is required to find relevant information. Little consideration is given to the drawbacks of Arab instructors teaching in Arab schools in Turkey.

Sahito & Vaisanen,2019, Legault et al. (2006) have claimed that in order to better understand the variables that motivate teacher educators in the Departments of Education at universities in Pakistan's Sindh region, a research study was carried out. The data was gathered and analyzed using the story analysis method, which was used as part of the qualitative study design. According to the findings of the article, the existing literature on motivation would be a suitable and reliable addition to the available literature. (Daniels & Arapostathis, 2005).

According to Toraman et al.,2020, Turkish instructors taught Turkish and Turkish culture to Turkish students in Germany and France. Researchers have detailed that Turkish instructors attempt to work in other countries for a number of reasons, with varying levels of success. The study's findings revealed that there was a specific driving factor that encouraged instructors to teach overseas. This driving energy manifested itself as a feeling of wonder and pride at having been selected to teach in another country.

Serbes,2017, has argued that teaching English in a foreign country has always been a fantastic opportunity for both academic and social growth. His article focuses on five reasons dealing with the issue why instructors choose to teach abroad rather than in their own country. It is critical to emphasize that instructors with foreign experience are more effective teachers who can make a greater contribution to the academic performance of their pupils. Teaching in a foreign country may assist instructors in developing their efficiency and effectiveness abilities. (Serbes, 2017).

Teaching overseas helps teachers socially and professionally. The research concludes that instructors need certain talents. Education is critical for future generations' progress. Teaching overseas may be beneficial.

6. Negative influences of homesickness

Niziurski & Berntsen,2018, determined that homesickness has been demonstrated to have a negative influence on a person's physical, social, and cognitive well-being, according to research. To create predictions, the authors used

personality, depression, and autobiographical memory measurements that were all gathered prior to deployment. The study's prospective approach and utilization of a military sample set it apart from past studies.(Niziurski & Berntsen, 2018).

Furthermore, this research discovered that some major groups in society, such as teachers in other countries, must be researched in order to disclose the influence of homesickness on individuals, as was the case in our study, in order to better understand the phenomena of homesickness.

According to Sumalinog,2021, This research looks at the experiences of 10 Filipino ESL and EFL teachers who live and work in different parts of the globe. Skype and Facebook Messenger are used to gather virtual data. According to the study, time spent in a foreign nation benefited teachers' professional life by strengthening their abilities. It was determined that before a teacher chose to go overseas, they all agreed that internal and external assistance should be available to ensure that working away from home could be tolerated. Researchers may delve deeply into the cultural interactions that informants have with their students and colleagues.(Sumalinog, 2021).

According to this study, there are two primary reasons for visiting abroad: First, there are monetary issues. Personal motivations are a further source of worry. This study investigates the reasons why foreign instructors seek jobs in other nations.

7. Factors that might affect homesickness

Nijhof & Engels, 2008, Students raised by authoritative or permissive parents are less likely to experience feelings of homesickness than students raised by permissive or uninvolved parents. Students with parents who advocated an authoritarian parenting style had more internalizing and externalization difficulties in response to feeling homesick; they also used less efficient coping mechanisms. The findings showed that a caring and welcoming home environment is critical for the development and expression of homesickness's(Nijhof & Engels, 2008).

In general, being able to recognize homesickness in students early on is crucial, as is not dismissing students who show their sadness by externalizing their problems.

The relevance of parents' responsiveness while raising children, for the development of homesickness, and for the way students cope with their issues, is highlighted by the mix of parenting styles that result in the expression of homesickness and the development of coping methods.

Eurelings-Bontekoe et al.,1994, have indicated that their research focuses on the personality traits and behavioral features of military soldiers who are missing their families. In thier study, the participants were divided into two groups: healthy volunteers and recruits suffering from various mental disorders. Despite the fact that the two uncontrolled groups have many characteristics in common with the healthy group, homesick subjects exhibit some distinct characteristics that are either not observed in the psychiatric control group. (Eurelings-Bontekoe et al., 1994).

Current study surveyed soldiers with severe homesickness to better understand their personality and behavioral antecedents. The research also identifies behavioral and psychological aspects that increase homesickness. This research revealed behavioral and psychological aspects that may increase homesickness.

Meeks, 1968, when children are admitted to residential treatment, they may feel severe homesickness. This disease seems to be linked to separation issues and an inability to develop internal self-esteem management. It is also essential to examine the ramifications of object loss, as well as efforts to recover the item. The triggering factors, including as home visits, staff rejection, and narcissistic traumas that occur both within and outside of therapy, are well addressed. We explain and show, using a case study, how the suggested techniques for active engagement with the child and his family may be utilized successfully(Meeks, 1968).

In order to produce healthy children, this research suggests that parents should monitor their children's development (1968). This sickness is caused by a lack of belief in one's own worth. Spending time with their family and learning to have a positive self-image may be advantageous for children (Meeks, 1968).

8. Dealing with Homesickness

Zulkarnain et al.,2019, maintained that students' perspective of a stressor may be changed by social support from peers in their new surroundings. Boys and girls may feel homesickness in a variety of situations, such as camp or boarding school, depending on their age. Students benefit from social assistance because it helps them adjust more quickly and make their experiences in unfamiliar settings more pleasant. According to the findings of this research, children with an authoritative parenting style are more likely to cope with difficult situations during the transition from home to college life. A good attitude at boarding schools may be fostered via activities or hobbies that foster interaction with others in the surrounding area of the boarding school(Zulkarnain et al., 2019).

The findings of this research suggest that significant progress has been made in understanding the reasons and circumstances that contribute to homesickness; nevertheless, the research does not explain how those factors may impact workers who are employed in other countries.

Saravanan et al., 2017, specified that students who study in foreign nations for their higher education experience a variety of psychological difficulties, including homesickness and depression. This study sought to identify differences between students who received and did not receive brief individual cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) for depression. The goal of the study was to determine whether brief individual CBT for depression reduces the level of homesickness (Saravanan et al., 2017).

The majority of foreign students are hesitant to seek help from mental health experts because of mental health fears and social stigma. 27.3 percent of the foreign students who were depressed were also suffering from homesickness. The researchers came to the conclusion that short cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) for depression is helpful. Mental health practitioners should use CBT as it is manual-based and helpful in the treatment of depression and depression symptoms (Saravanan et al., 2017).

This study is a noteworthy addition to the field since it demonstrates the progress that has been done in the studies of homesickness and its effects on particular vulnerable groups, such as students. Despite the fact that the scope of this study has been expanded to include strategies for dealing with the real-world ramifications of this theoretical notion, it has remained concentrated on the theoretical concept itself.

Furthermore, unlike in our research, there is no proof of professors who really teach in other countries, which is an issue that must be addressed.

Hendrickson et al., 2011, stated that in this study, students from the host country and other nations become friends with foreign students. More host country friends have been linked to higher levels of social connectedness and pleasure. Less than half of foreign students polled said they were content with their lives. In contrast to previous studies, foreign students had less native contacts. (Hendrickson et al., 2011).

This study contributes to the field of research on cross-cultural adaptation by examining how foreign students utilize social resources while studying abroad. It uses a novel, comprehensive technique for evaluating individual buddy networks and network theory concepts to explain observed occurrences. Most significantly, this study's results show the value of having both strong and weak ties with locals in one's social network (Hendrickson et al., 2011). This research, which contributes to the existing body of information on cross-cultural adaptation, explores the ways in which foreign students make use of financial help while they are studying abroad. Again, this research reveals tremendous advancement in the study of the concept of homesickness; yet, a vacuum still exists in all of these literatures, and that vacuum is the study of the influence that homesickness has on the work flow of foreign workers.

M. Al Van Tilburg et al., 1999, Researchers have carried out a research on female students of coping strategies and essential personality types. The selection of homesick female students split in those who were homesick chronically and those who had not, to examine if certain coping methods and personality types were related with homesickness chronicity. Analyzes of logistic regression showed that Coping Style, mental flight and the personality attribute of neuroticism forecasts the chronicity of home disease. Since neuroticism has a greater influence on the quick recovery of household disease than any coping technique, personality is more important than coping style (M. Al Van Tilburg et al., 1999). The conclusion reached by the researchers' shows that the major objective of the study was to investigate the possibility of treating homesickness via a variety of different ways.

9. Ways to cope with the negative emotions

According to Kaur et al., 2021, Pre-service teachers (PST) benefit professionally and personally by participating in an International Teaching Practicum (ITP). Challenges encountered during ITPs can act as stresses, obstructing PSTs' learning and harming their emotional and psychological well-being, which may affect their identity as future teachers. In this research, we looked into the experiences of 12 PSTs during their foreign teaching practicum (Kaur et al., 2021).

The phenomena studied in this research was PSTs' support system experiences during ITP. The majority of the data was associated with emotional experiences, and categorizing a few of them proved to be a tough job. Four main themes emerged from the data analysis, each of which had numerous sub themes. "His presence (the supervisor) lifted my mood like a caffeine kick early in the morning," has a connotation of positive emotional well-being as well as a motivational appeal to continue with zeal and enthusiasm with the practicum requirement (Kaur et al., 2021).

10. Dealing with homesickness academically

As per Archer et al., 1998, Fisher Hood and his co-authors examined the association between the scale's component structure and happiness, as well as whether the person left their spouse at home. The results for the comparison of homesick and non-homesick groups on the MHQ scales and the CFQ corroborated past findings, and the meta-analysis of current and previous data showed that all five measures were significantly higher among homesick students. Data from three samples were analyzed by examining the scale's factor structure, comparing each item in groups based on their scores on Fisher Hood's single-item measure of homesickness, and calculating correlations between the 33-item questionnaire's total scores and Fisher Hood's single-item measure (1987, 1988). A single-item homesickness scale

correlates well with the CFQ and MHQ. Correlations varied from .62 for depression to .89 for obsessional symptoms. Every loss must be evaluated against prospective advantages.

Conclusion

Several articles and books on the topic of "Homesickness" have been mentioned during the course of this study. The academic works covered in these articles all dealt with "Homesickness" in various ways. Numerous publications have addressed the conceptual side of it, and this was in the very beginning, when the idea initially emerged and began to be acknowledged.

Other study has addressed the nature and realism of this idea, as well as the issue of whether it is a physiological or physical entity. Other articles have elaborated on the elements that might be responsible for this sentiment. Others have investigated the potentially harmful repercussions of such emotions, as well as the variables that create an environment in which they may appear and become prominent. Significant study has been conducted on the topic of "Homesickness," and these findings have been published. Some experts have focused their attention on the phenomenon known as "Homesickness," which affects youngsters when they are in unfamiliar environments like a nursery or school. The consequences of "Homesickness" on students is a topic that has been researched by a number of other academics. In conclusion, the literature review came to the conclusion that this body of material is missing in the area of the affects that "Homesickness" has on the flow of work.

As a direct consequence of this, the investigation into the impact of "Homesickness" on the daily operations of Arab schools in Ankara is a new subject that has to be discussed.

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